

QUANTITATIVE OF PLATELETS AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF ANTI-VIRUS THERAPY IN CHRONIC HEPATITIS WITH HCV ETIOLOGY.

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Background. Liver disease leads to impaired blood clotting mainly due to malfunction of platelet adhesion and aggregation. [7]. This dysfunction is related to the activity of specific enzymes and transaminases in the liver [3,6]. An increase in the activity of transaminases is a sign of cytolytic syndrome, in which a decrease in platelet aggregation is observed [1.].

In the last decade, significant changes were noted in the laboratory diagnosis of severe diffuse liver diseases associated with coagulation and fibrinolysis systems. [2].

Aim. The purpose of the study. Evaluation of the amount of platelets against the background of antiviral therapy in chronic hepatitis of HCV etiology.

Material and methods. The data were collected from patients treated with HCV-etiological diseases hepatitis at the Department of Hematology and Hepatobiliary Pathology of the 1st Clinic of the Tashkent Medical Academy in 2020-2023.

Results. In 20 patients who did not receive antiviral therapy, the platelet count was $216 \pm 45 \times 10^9/l$, while in 30 patients who received antiviral therapy, the platelet count before treatment was $232 \pm 50 \times 10^9/l$, and after 1 month of treatment, the platelet count was $221 \pm 46 \times 10^9/l$, after 3 months of treatment it was equal to $203 \pm 42 \times 10^9/l$.

Conclusions. In patients with chronic hepatitis of HCV etiology, the platelet count was at the level of normal indicators, and in 30 patients with SGV of HCV

etiology, who received antiviral therapy, the platelet count did not reliably change in patients who received AVT for 3 months.

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